

O'ZBEKISTONDA YO'L XARAKATI XAVFSIZLIGI

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani 2 son kasb hunar maktabi
yo'l harakati qoidalari fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonda yo'l harakati xavfsizligi tarixiga qisqacha to'xtab o'tilgan. 1936 yilning 3 iyul sanasida Sobiq Sovet Ittifoqida Davlat avtomobil nazorati haqidagi birinchi Nizom tasdiqlanganligi, 3-iyul kuni rasmiy ravishda Davlat avtomobil nazorati xizmati tashkil etilgan kun hisoblanishi haqida qiziqarli ma'lumotlar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: Yo'l, harakat, tarix, nizom, o'quvchi, avtomobil

Аннотация: В статье кратко рассматривается история обеспечения безопасности дорожного движения в Узбекистане. 3 июля 1936 года имеются интересные сведения об утверждении первого Положения о государственном контроле транспортных средств на территории бывшего Советского Союза, а 3 июля является днем официального создания Службы государственного контроля транспортных средств.

Ключевые слова: Дорога, движение, история, регулирование, студент, автомобиль.

Abstract: The article briefly examines the history of road safety in Uzbekistan. On July 3, 1936, there is interesting information about the approval of the first Regulations on state control of vehicles in the territory of the former Soviet Union, and July 3 is the day of the official creation of the State Control of Vehicles Service.

Key words: Road, traffic, history, regulation, student, car.

O'zbekistonda yo'l xarakati xavfsizligi bilan alohida shug'illanadigan tashkilot mavjud. Uning tarixini kasb hunar maktablari o'quvchilariga fanning ilk soatlarida og'zaki tushuntirilib boriladi.

Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi xizmatining tarixi 1936 yilning 3 iyul sanasida Sobiq Sovet Ittifoqida Davlat avtomobil nazorati haqidagi birinchi Nizom tasdiqlangan. 3-iyul kuni rasmiy ravishda Davlat avtomobil nazorati xizmati tashkil etilgan kun hisoblanadi. Dastlab Sobiq Sovet Sosialistik Respublikasi Ittifoqi Yo'ltrans markaziy boshqarmasi qoshidagi Davlat avtomobil nazorati boshlig'ining 1935 yilda imzolangan 2-sonli buyrug'i bilan asli venesiyalik chilangar usta 1934 yildan boshlab O'zavtoyo'ltrans direktori bo'lib ishlagan Xorvat Yuzef Karlovich O'zbekiston Sovet Sosialistik Respublikasi Davlat avtomobil nazorati xizmatining boshlig'i etib tayinlangan.

Ikkinchi jahon urushi va undan keyingi davrlardan tortib Davlat mustaqilligi qabul qilinguniga qadar ham qator o'z kasbining fidoiylari sharaflil xizmatga rahbarlik qilibgina qolmay, uning rivoji uchun o'zlarining munosib hissalarini qo'shishgan:

O'tgan asrning ikkinchi yarmida yo'llarda harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, jamoat tartibini saqlash borasida fidoiylilik ko'rsatgan yo'l boshqaruvchisi, milisiya starshinasi Sodiq Qosimovning xizmatlari beqiyos bo'lgan. U Toshkent milisiyasida 25 yil mobaynida xizmat qilgan. Sodiq xizmatlari uchun "Qizil bayroq", "Qizil yulduz" ordenlari, "SHaraflil mehnati uchun" medallari, "Besh yillik zarbdori" unvoniga sazovor bo'lgan. Uning shaxsiy yig'ma jildida 83 ta rag'batlantirish yozilgan bo'lgan.

Yo'l harakati xavfsizligi xizmati bugun keng tarmoqli, ko'p vazifali safarbar xizmatlar sirasiga kiradi:

- yo'llarda harakat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, qoidabuzarliklarga chek qo'yish, uning oqibatida sodir bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan yo'l-transport hodisalarining

oldini olish maqsadida xizmat o'tovchi yo'l-patrol xizmati faoliyatini tashkil etish bo'limi;

- avtomobil yo'llari holatining doimiy nazorati, svetoforlarning aniq ishlashi, yo'l belgilarining to'g'ri o'rnatilishi, qatnov qismini ajratib turuvchi chiziqlarni belgilash, ko'priklar yo'l o'tkazmalari va temir yo'l kesishmalari, avtomobil yo'llari qurilishi ustidan nazoratni amalga oshiruvchi yo'l harakatini tashkil etishni nazorat qilish bo'linmasi;

- avtomototransport vositalari texnik holatining belgilangan me'yorlarga javob berishini, bu bilan yo'llarimizda texnik soz avtomobillar harakatini ta'minlovchi transport vositalarining texnik holati ustidan nazoratni tashkil etish bo'limi;

-yo'l harakati ishtirokchilari tomonidan sodir etiladigan qoidabuzarliklarni aniqlab, tegishli ta'sir choralarini qo'llash, transport vositalari bilan bog'liq har qanday turdagi huquqbuzarliklarga qarshi kurashishni ta'minlovchi yo'l harakati doirasidagi qonunbuzarliklar bilan kurashish bo'linmasi;

- avtomototransport vositasi hisobini olib borish va ro'yxatlash, davlat raqam belgilari, avtomototransport vositalarini boshqarish huquqini beruvchi guvohnomalarni berish, haydovchi kadrlar tayyorlashni nazorat qiluvchi ro'yxatlash va imtihon olish ishlarini tashkillashtirish va nazorat qilish bo'linmasi;

- yo'l harakati qatnashchilarini yo'l-transport hodisalaridan himoya qilish darajasini oshirish, qoidabuzarliklarni xizmatga kirib kelgan zamonaviy texnikalar yordamida avtomatik tarzda aniqlash, qayd etish va profilaktika ishlarini bugungi kun talabi darajasida takomillashtirish faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi yo'l harakati xavfsizligining markaziy kompyuterlashtirilgan boshqaruvi, aloqa va axborot kommunikasiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish boshqarmasi;

- huquqbuzarliklarga nisbatan tuzilgan ma'muriy bayonnomalarning huquqiy asoslarini ko'rib chiqib, qoidabuzarliklarga Qonunda belgilangan tartibda ma'muriy choralar qo'llashni nazarda tutuvchi ma'muriy amaliyot xizmati;

- fuqarolar o'rtasida yo'l harakati xavfsizligi doirasida to'g'ridan-to'g'ri keng targ'ibot ishlarini amalga oshirish, ommaviy axborot vositalari bilan hamkorlikda turli ko'rsatuv, lavha va roliklar tayyorlab, fuqarolarning yo'l harakati qoidalariga rioya etishlarini targ'ib qilishni tashkillashtiruvchi Axborot xizmati hamda qator bo'lim, bo'linma va guruhlar faoliyati Davlat yo'l harakati xavfsizligi xizmati negizida yo'lga qo'yilgan.

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